

Efficacy and safety of SGLT2 inhibitors in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: a systematic review

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Abstract

Selective sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors act only at the renal level, promoting glucose excretion. Their glucose-independent mechanism makes them effective in advanced type 2 diabetes mellitus, when pancreatic β -cell reserves are permanently reduced. In addition to glucosuria, SGLT2 inhibition induces natriuresis, contributing to negative salt and water balance. The aim of this study is to evaluate the efficacy and safety of SGLT2 inhibitors in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus through a systematic review of scientific publications, examining clinical trials with this class of glucose-lowering medicinal products. We performed a literature search in MEDLINE, the Central Library of Medicine, and peer-reviewed journals for the period January 2004 to December 2024. The systematic review is conducted in accordance with the PRISMA standard and the PICOS tool. The results of the PICOS analysis show that the most significant reduction in HbA1c level is observed after administration of Ertugliflozin 15 mg (–0.90%) and Ipragliflozin 50 mg (–0.88%). The body weight reduction is the most significant after administration of Ertugliflozin 15 mg, by 2.93 kg. Common adverse drug reactions include urinary tract infections and genital mycotic infections. The results of the conducted PICOS analysis prove the high efficacy of SGLT2 inhibitors in terms of their cardiovascular safety and cardio-renal benefits. In addition to their glucose-lowering properties, they are associated with a very low risk of hypoglycemia.

Keywords

diabetes mellitus, efficacy, HbA1c, safety, SGLT2 inhibitors, systematic review

Introduction

Over the last two decades, new therapeutic options for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus have been introduced, which significantly improved disease control and the overall quality of life of patients. However, due to the heterogeneity of the etiology and diabetes-related complications, maintaining good glycemic control remains a

challenge. There are two main sodium-glucose cotransporters in the human body: sodium-glucose cotransporter 1 (SGLT1) and sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2). SGLT2 cotransporters are expressed almost exclusively in renal tissue, while SGLT1 is found mainly in the small intestine, as well as in the heart, skeletal muscles, and kidneys. In the proximal tubules of the nephron, these two transporters carry out the reabsorption of

sodium and glucose from the glomerular filtrate. SGLT2 cotransporters have a high transport capacity and low affinity for glucose and are responsible for the reabsorption of approximately 90–97% of filtered glucose under normal conditions. The remaining 3–10% of filtered glucose is reabsorbed via the SGLT1 cotransporter. Selective SGLT2 inhibitors act only at the renal level, allowing glucose excretion and functioning as osmotic diuretics. Due to their glucose-independent mechanism of action, this class is effective in advanced type 2 diabetes mellitus, when pancreatic β -cell reserves are permanently reduced. SGLT2 inhibition also causes natriuresis, leading to a clinically significant reduction in plasma volume and blood pressure. A reduction of approximately 3–6 mmHg in systolic blood pressure and 1–1.5 mmHg in diastolic blood pressure is commonly observed. The first oral SGLT2 inhibitor, T-1095, demonstrated a reduction in HbA1c, microalbuminuria, and weight loss in rats. However, it lacked selectivity for SGLT2, and inhibition of intestinal SGLT1 led to significant gastrointestinal adverse reactions. Current representatives of the SGLT2 inhibitor class are significantly more selective, with a good safety profile and proven cardiorenal benefits (Tankova 2013; Chaudhury et al. 2017; Rehani et al. 2019).

According to current guidelines for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus, issued by the American Diabetes Association (ADA) and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes (EASD), in adult patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and established or high risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), heart failure (HF), or chronic kidney disease (CKD), the treatment plan should include a medicinal product with proven cardiorenal benefits, such as SGLT2 inhibitors and glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonists. Both classes are associated with a low risk of hypoglycemia (ADA 2024) (Table 1).

Table 1. Doses and dose ranges of SGLT2 inhibitors.

INN	Dose range	Dose
Canagliflozin	1× daily	100–300 mg
Dapagliflozin	1× daily	10 mg
Empagliflozin	1× daily	10–25 mg
Ertugliflozin	1× daily	5–15 mg
Ipragliflozin	1× daily	50–100 mg
Bexagliflozin	1× daily	20 mg

Dapagliflozin increases sodium delivery to the distal tubules, which reduces intraglomerular pressure, which, in combination with osmotic diuresis, leads to a reduction in volume overload, lowered blood pressure, and reduced preload and afterload, which may have beneficial effects on cardiac remodeling and diastolic function, as well as preservation of renal function. Dapagliflozin improves both postprandial and fasting blood glucose levels by increasing urinary glucose excretion. This urinary excretion is observed after the first dose, is maintained throughout the 24-hour dosing interval, and continues throughout the treatment period (EMA 2024).

Empagliflozin does not inhibit other glucose transporters that are important for glucose transport in peripheral tissues and is 5000 times more selective for SGLT2 than for SGLT1. In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, urinary glucose excretion increases immediately after the first dose of Empagliflozin and remains so for the 24-hour dosing interval. Increased urinary glucose excretion persists until the end of the 4-week follow-up period and averages approximately 78 g/day (EMA 2025).

For the period 2012–2024, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) has issued marketing authorizations for six medicinal products belonging to the SGLT2 inhibitor class. The approved medicinal products are distributed into four INNs, respectively: Dapagliflozin, Canagliflozin, Empagliflozin, and Ertugliflozin. The first authorized SGLT2 inhibitor for use was Dapagliflozin in 2012 (EMA 2012). Canagliflozin was authorized for use on 15/11/2013, Empagliflozin on 22/05/2014, and Ertugliflozin on 21/03/2018 (EMA 2013; EMA 2014; EMA 2018). Ipragliflozin is the first SGLT2 inhibitor to be approved in Japan. Ipragliflozin received its first global approval for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus in Japan in 2014 (Poole and Dungo 2014). Bexagliflozin received its first approval in the USA in January 2023 for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus and essential hypertension (Hoy 2023).

Aim

The aim of this study is to perform a retrospective systematic review of scientific publications that evaluate the efficacy and safety of SGLT2 inhibitors in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The primary endpoints assessed are change in glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) level from baseline, effect of the investigational medicinal product on body weight, and the occurrence of adverse events during the analyzed clinical trials.

Methods

The systematic review is conducted in accordance with the recommendations of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Fig. 1). PRISMA is an evidence-based minimum set of recommendations, which improve the reporting of systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Moher et al. 2009; Shamseer et al. 2015; PRISMA 2025). The study protocol is developed in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 Checklist. We pre-defined the study topic, study design, search strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and methods of data collection and analysis. The PRISMA 2020 statement is designed for systematic reviews of studies that evaluate the effects of health interventions, irrespective of the design of the included studies (Hutton et al. 2015; Page et al. 2021). We conducted a retrospective observational study by reviewing scientific publications in English and Bulgarian, using the following keywords: diabetes mellitus type 2, SGLT2 inhibitors, efficacy, safety, clinical trial, and HbA1c. The search

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram.

of scientific publications was conducted in MEDLINE, the Central Library of Medicine, and refereed scientific journal databases for the period January 2004 to December 2024. Over the 20-year search period, a total of 360 scientific publications were identified. We extracted the following data from the included studies: first author's surname, year of publication, clinical trial design, clinical trial number and duration, study population, demographics, duration of diabetes, previous glucose-lowering therapy before the start of the clinical trial, baseline glycated hemoglobin level before initiation of the clinical trial, primary endpoints, efficacy data (Figs 2, 3), and safety data by evaluation of the adverse events occurring during the analyzed clinical trials (Table 8) (National Library of Medicine 2024; EUDRACT 2024). Two of the authors, independently of each other, extracted data from the research articles that met the inclusion criteria.

We also performed a documentary and PICOS (Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes, Study design) analysis of the conducted clinical trials with the SGLT2 inhibitor class. The PICO analysis includes four components of health: P—"patient, population, or problem," which describes the characteristics of the patient or population (demographics, risk factors, comorbidities) and the condition or disease; I—"Intervention," which describes the intervention that is applied; C—"Comparison," in which the administration of the investigational

medicinal product against placebo or against established glucose-lowering therapy is compared; O—"Result/s," in which results related to quality of life, change in clinical status, morbidity, adverse events, and development of complications are presented. In the modified version, PICOS, "S" refers to the study design (Thomas et al. 2024).

Results

The selection of the analyzed scientific articles is presented as a PRISMA flow diagram (Fig. 1).

The literature search was restricted to articles published in English and Bulgarian. In the initial search, we found 360 scientific publications. We analyzed all 360 abstracts and searched for full-text articles. A total of 142 articles were excluded because they did not include the following keywords: type 2 diabetes mellitus, SGLT2 inhibitor, Canagliflozin, Dapagliflozin, Empagliflozin, Ertugliflozin, Ipragliflozin, and Bexagliflozin. At the final stage, of the remaining 218 articles, 177 full-text articles were excluded due to the absence of data on clinical trial design, efficacy, safety, and glycated hemoglobin level. A total of 41 scientific publications met our initial inclusion criteria and were included in the analysis of clinical trials, which evaluate the efficacy and safety of SGLT2 inhibitors.

Figure 2. Relative proportions of HbA1c level reduction for different SGLT2 inhibitors.

Figure 3. Comparison between SGLT2 inhibitors in terms of body weight reduction.

To evaluate the results obtained, we used PICOS analysis (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes, Study design) (Higgins et al. 2013; Methley et al. 2014). Adverse events occurring during the analyzed clinical trials are presented according to the MedDRA systemic organ classification, version 28.1, and the common terminological criteria for adverse events (MedDRA 2025). The results of the differentiated PICOS analysis of SGLT2 inhibitors are presented in tabular form (Tables 2–7) by INN (Petrova 2025).

Canagliflozin

Canagliflozin has been administered in 14 clinical trials, of which 11 were placebo-controlled, one was active-controlled, and two were placebo- and active-controlled. They lasted between 12 and 104 weeks, and all were randomized. Seven of the clinical trials lasted for 52 weeks. The total number of patients was 9,505. The interventions administered were Canagliflozin 50, 100, 200, or 300 mg administered once daily. In one of the clinical trials, Canagliflozin

was administered in combination with insulin therapy. In 11 of the trials, Canagliflozin was compared with placebo; in two, it was compared with placebo and with Sitagliptin 100 mg; and in one, it was compared with Glimepiride (up to 6 mg or 8 mg daily). Results regarding efficacy for HbA1c reduction show that Canagliflozin 100 mg reduces HbA1c levels by -0.73% and Canagliflozin 300 mg by -0.84% . We calculated that the reduction in body weight with Canagliflozin 100 mg is by 2.1 kg and with Canagliflozin 300 mg is by 2.9 kg. The mean reduction in systolic blood pressure after administration of Canagliflozin 100 mg and Canagliflozin 300 mg is by -4.3 mmHg and -5.5 mmHg, respectively. The mean reduction in diastolic pressure is by -2.13 mmHg and -2.55 mmHg. The most common adverse events manifested in the course of the analyzed trials are urinary tract infections, genital mycotic infections, adverse events related to osmotic diuresis, pollakiuria, and polyuria. A decrease in triglyceride level, an increase in HDL-C level, and a decrease in liver enzymes ASAT, ALAT, and GGT (gamma-glutamyl transferase) are reported. Increased ketone body levels are reported in two of the trials.

Table 2. PICOS Canagliflozin.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 146 Japanese patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) with poor glycemic control despite being on insulin therapy 12 weeks prior to the start of the clinical trial. Average age: 56.1–59.7 years. Average body weight: 69.95 kg. Duration of T2DM: 12.34–15.18 years. Baseline HbA1c level: 8.85–8.89%. (Inagaki et al. 2016)	Canagliflozin 100 mg once daily before breakfast	Placebo	Mean HbA1c level reduction: –0.97% with Canagliflozin 100 mg Average weight reduction: –2.13 +/- 0.25% or –1.49 kg with Canagliflozin 100 mg. Systolic blood pressure decreased by –3.58 mmHg, and diastolic pressure decreased by –1.55 mmHg. Triglyceride levels decreased by –7.8 mg/dL at week 16 in the Canagliflozin group.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented hypoglycemia: 40%. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Osmotic diuresis: 5.3%; Polyuria: 4%; Pollakiuria: 5.3% Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 1.3%. Genital mycotic infection: 3.2% Investigations: Slight increase in ketone bodies (59.93 µmol/L) from baseline in the Canagliflozin group.	16-week, randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02220920
N = 218, aged 18–75 years with T2DM poorly controlled with maximum doses of Metformin (≥1500 mg/day) and Sitagliptin 100 mg/day ≥ 12 weeks prior to the start of the trial. Baseline HbA1c level: ≥ 7.5–≤10.5%. (Rodbard et al. 2016)	Canagliflozin 100 mg once daily. After 6 weeks, the dose of Canagliflozin was titrated from 100 mg to 300 mg.	Placebo	Average HbA1c level reduction: –0.91%. Fasting plasma glucose (FPG) reduction: –1.65 mmol/L. Body weight reduction: –3.4% or –1.6 kg with Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg. Systolic blood pressure (SBP) reduction: –5.8 mmHg with Canagliflozin. Diastolic blood pressure (DBP) reduction: –3.3 mmHg with Canagliflozin.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 3.7% Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections 12.2%. Urinary tract infection: 1.9%. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Osmotic diuresis-related adverse events: 5.6% Polyuria: 2.78%	26-week, randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, multicenter, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02025907
N = 716, aged ≥ 55 and ≤ 80 years with T2DM. Baseline HbA1c level: ≥ 7.0%–≤10.0% (Bode et al. 2015)	Canagliflozin 100 mg or 300 mg once daily	Placebo	Mean HbA1c level reduction: –0.50% and –0.60% with Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg. Mean body weight reduction with Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg: –2.1 kg and –2.9 kg. Reduction of systolic blood pressure by –5.8 mmHg and –7.5 mmHg and of diastolic blood pressure by –1.5 and –2.6 mmHg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented hypoglycemia: 54.1–61.0%; Severe hypoglycemia: 2.9% Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 14.5–16.5%; Genital mycotic infections: 18.7–23.9%. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Osmotic diuresis-related adverse events: 9.1–12.3%	104-week, randomized double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01106651
N = 2074, with T2DM, on insulin therapy (mean daily insulin dose 60 IU). Baseline HbA1c level: 8.3%. Body mass index (BMI): 33.1 kg/m ² . Estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR): 75 mL/min/1.73 m ² . Fasting plasma glucose (FPG): 9.2 mmol/L. (Neal et al. 2015)	Canagliflozin 100 mg or 300 mg in combination with insulin therapy (insulin dose ≥ 20 IU/day)	Placebo	Mean HbA1c level reduction: –0.62% and –0.73% at week 18 and –0.58% and –0.73% at week 52 with Canagliflozin 100 mg or 300 mg. Body weight reduction: –2.8% to –3.5%. Systolic blood pressure reduction: –3.1 mmHg to –6.2 mmHg. Diastolic blood pressure reduction: –1.2 mmHg to –2.4 mmHg. The triglyceride levels decreased by: –1.6% and –5.6%.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented hypoglycemia: 57–59%, of which severe hypoglycemia: 6%. Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections in women: 13–18%. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Osmotic diuresis-associated adverse events: 9–10%. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Fractures: 1–3%	52-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group, multicenter trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01032629

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 272 Japanese patients with T2DM, aged ≥ 20 years, who controlled the disease only with an appropriate diet and exercise. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.0–10.0% (Inagaki et al. 2014)	Canagliflozin 100 or 200 mg once daily	Placebo	Decrease in HbA1c level: -0.74% and -0.76%. Body weight reduction: -3.76% and -4.02% or -3.0 kg and -3.26 kg. Reduction of systolic blood pressure by -7.88 mmHg and -6.24 mmHg. Decrease in diastolic blood pressure by -4.44 and -2.66 mmHg. HDL-C level increased significantly in both groups on Canagliflozin therapy. LDL-C was elevated in both Canagliflozin groups.	Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections in women: 6.5% and 6.3%. Urinary tract infection: 1.1% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Symptomatic hypoglycemia: 2.2% and 1.1%; Asymptomatic hypoglycemia: 4.4% and 5.6%. Investigations: reduction of ASAT by -4.0 and -2.5 U/l, reduction of ALAT by -7.0 and -3.9 U/l.	24-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicenter trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01413204
N = 342, with T2DM, on therapy with Metformin and Pioglitazone. Age ≥ 18 and ≤ 80 years, FPG < 15 mmol/l. Baseline HbA1c level: ≥ 7.0% to ≤ 10.5%. (Forst et al. 2014)	Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg	Placebo during a 26-week, placebo-controlled period and a subsequent 26-week, active-controlled period in which patients switched to therapy with Sitagliptin 100 mg.	Mean HbA1c level reduction at week 26: -0.89% and -1.03% with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg. Mean HbA1c level reduction at week 52: -0.92% and -1.03%. Body weight reduction: -2.5 kg and -3.6 kg. Decrease in systolic blood pressure at week 52: -3.4 mmHg and -3.7 mmHg with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg. Decrease in diastolic blood pressure by: -3.5 and -2.7 mmHg.	Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections: 16.7%–21.6% Urinary tract infection: 5.3–7.9% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Osmotic diuresis-related adverse events: 9.6–9.7% Pollakiuria: 5.31% and 7.02% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented episodes of hypoglycemia: 2.65% and 4.39%.	52-week, randomized, double-blind trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01106690
N = 584, with T2DM, poorly controlled with an appropriate diet and exercise. HbA1c level at baseline: 7.0–10.0%. (Stenlöf et al. 2014)	Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg	Placebo	Mean HbA1c level reduction by: -0.81% and -1.11%. Reduction of FPG by -1.5 and -2.2 mmol/L. Body weight reduction: -3.3% and -4.4% or -2.8 kg and -3.9 kg. Reduction of systolic blood pressure by -1.4 mmHg and -3.9 mmHg. Reduction of diastolic blood pressure by -0.4 mmHg and -0.7 mmHg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented episodes of hypoglycaemia over 52 weeks: 5.1% and 3.6%. Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infections: 7.1–8.2%; Genital mycotic infections: 9.3–11.4%. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Osmotic diuresis-related adverse events: 4.6–7.6%. Investigations: Increase in HDL-C: percentage change from 11.1% and 14.7%. Reduction of triglyceride levels by -2.0% and -2.1%.	52-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01081834

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 469, aged 18–80 years with T2DM who had poor glycemic control on maximum dose therapy with Metformin and sulphonylurea. Average body weight: 92.8 kg. HbA1c level at baseline: $\geq 7.0\%$ – $\leq 10.5\%$. (Wilding et al. 2013)	Canagliflozin 100 or 300 mg once daily	Placebo	Reduction of HbA1c level at week 26: -0.85% and -1.06% , at week 52: -0.75% and -0.97% . At week 26 Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg decreased body weight with: -1.4% (-1.1 kg) and -2.0% (-1.7 kg). At week 52, the body weight reduction was: -1.3% (-2.1 , -0.5 kg) and -2.2% (-3.0 , -1.4 kg) with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg. At week 52, the decrease in systolic blood pressure was by: -3.7 mmHg and -3.0 mmHg. Decrease of diastolic blood pressure by: -2.2 mmHg and -1.7 mmHg. Improvement in β cell function was observed with both doses of Canagliflozin.	Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections in men: 5.7–7.6%; in women: 18.5–18.8%. Urinary tract infection: 7.64% and 5.77% Nasopharyngitis: 7.73% and 7.77% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Osmotic diuresis-related adverse events, pollakiuria, polyuria: 5.7–7.1%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented hypoglycemic episodes: 33.8–36.5%. Severe hypoglycemia: 0.6%. Investigations: At week 52, there was an increase in baseline HDL-C and triglyceride levels with both doses of Canagliflozin. Moderate reduction of gamma glutamyl transferase with -12.3% and -8.6% .	52-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01106625
N = 1284 with T2DM aged ≥ 18 and ≤ 80 years, with poor glycemic control, on therapy with Metformin (≥ 2000 mg/day or ≥ 1500 mg/day). Baseline HbA1c level: $\geq 7.0\%$ and $\leq 10.5\%$. (Lavalle-González et al. 2013)	Canagliflozin 100 mg or 300 mg	Sitagliptin 100 mg or placebo.	At week 26, Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg reduced HbA1c level by -0.79% and -0.94% . At week 52, Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg reduced the HbA1c level with -0.73% and -0.88% . At week 26, Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg reduced body weight by: -3.7% and -4.2% . At week 52, Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg significantly reduced body weight compared to Sitagliptin with -2.4% (-2.1 kg) and -2.9% (-2.5 kg). Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg significantly reduced systolic blood pressure compared to Sitagliptin at week 52: -2.9 and -4.0 mmHg. Both doses of Canagliflozin increased HDL-cholesterol levels and LDL-cholesterol levels.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented episodes of hypoglycemia over 52 weeks were 6.8% with both doses of Canagliflozin. All groups showed a decrease in eGFR. Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections: Male: 2.4–5.2% Female: 9.9–11.3% Urinary tract infection: 4.63–7.34% Nasopharyngitis: 4.36–4.89% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 3.0–5.71% Polyuria: 0.5%. Investigations: For 52 weeks, a decrease in alanine aminotransferase was observed with Canagliflozin.	A 52-week, randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, four-arm, placebo- and active-controlled trial at 169 centers in 22 countries. A 26-week placebo- and active-controlled, double-blind treatment period (Period I), followed by a 26-week active-controlled, double-blind treatment period (Period II). ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01106677

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 1450, aged 18–80 years with T2DM, on Metformin therapy ≥ 2000 mg per day or ≥ 1500 mg per day. HbA1c level at baseline: 7.0–9.5% (Cefalu et al. 2013)	Canagliflozin 100 mg or 300 mg once daily	Glimepiride (up to 6 mg or 8 mg daily)	Mean HbA1c level reduction at week 52: -0.82% and -0.93% for Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg. The percentage change in body weight was with -4.2% and -4.7% or -3.7 kg and -4.0 kg. Canagliflozin moderately reduced systolic blood pressure (-3.3 and -4.6 mmHg) and diastolic blood pressure (-1.8 and -2.5 mmHg) compared to Glimepiride. Canagliflozin was associated with an increase in HDL-cholesterol (7.9–9.0%) and a reduction in triglyceride level.	Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infections (6% for both doses of Canagliflozin. In the Canagliflozin 100 mg and 300 mg groups, a higher number of genital mycotic infections were reported (women: 11% and 14%; men: 7% and 8%). Renal and urinary tract disorders: Osmotic diuresis-related adverse events: pollakiuria: 3% for both doses of Canagliflozin; polyuria: < 1% for both doses. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: The incidence of severe hypoglycemia was lower with Canagliflozin 100 mg (<1%) and 300 mg (<1%) than with Glimepiride (3%).	A 52-week, randomized, double-blind, active-controlled trial at 157 centers in 19 countries. ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT00968812
N = 383, aged 20–80 years, with T2DM, diagnosed ≥ 3 months ago, treated with diet and exercise alone. HbA1c level at baseline: 6.9–9.9% (Inagaki et al. 2013)	Canagliflozin 50, 100, 200, or 300 mg once daily	Placebo once daily	On the 12th week, the decrease in the HbA1c level with Canagliflozin 50, 100, 200, or 300 mg was, respectively, -0.61 , -0.80 , -0.79 , and -0.88% . Body weight reduction: -1.98 kg, -2.51 kg, -2.39 kg, -3.19 kg Reduction of systolic blood pressure by: -5.8 ± 1.2 mmHg -7.1 ± 1.2 mmHg -9.3 ± 1.2 mmHg -8.7 ± 1.2 mmHg Diastolic blood pressure reduction by: -2.2 ± 0.8 mmHg -3.9 ± 0.9 mmHg -5.1 ± 0.8 mmHg -4.2 ± 0.8 mmHg	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 9.8%, 13.5%, 10.4%, and 12%. Upper respiratory tract infections: 6.76%, 3.90%, 1.33%. 2 vulvovaginal candida infections in the Canagliflozin 100 (1.35%) and 300 mg (1.33%) groups. Investigations: Elevated ketone bodies: 4.9%, 6.8%, 11.7%, 8.0%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 3.7%, 2.7%, 2.6%, and 1.3% Dehydration: 1.33% in the Canagliflozin 300 mg group. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria in the Canagliflozin 50, 100, and 300 mg groups: 1.22%, 1.35%, and 1.33%. Gastrointestinal disorders: Gastritis: 1.3–1.4%	A 12-week multicenter, randomized, placebo-controlled, parallel-group trial. ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01022112
N = 714, aged 55–80 years with T2DM, who were on monotherapy or combined glucose-lowering therapy. HbA1c level at baseline: $\geq 7.0\%$ – $\leq 10.0\%$. (Bode et al. 2013)	Canagliflozin 100 mg or 300 mg	Placebo	Mean HbA1c level reduction by: -0.60% , -0.73% ; more participants achieved an HbA1c level < 7.0% with both doses of Canagliflozin. Body weight reduction: -2.3% (-2.1 kg) and -3.0% (-2.7 kg). Reduction of systolic blood pressure by: -4.6 mmHg and -7.9 mmHg. Reduction of diastolic blood pressure: -1.6 mmHg and -3.2 mmHg. Increase in HDL-C level by 5.3% and 4.7%.	Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections: Male: 3.2–6.2%; Female: 11.2–15.4% Urinary tract infection: 5.81–8.1% Nasopharyngitis: 8.05–9.54% Upper respiratory tract infection: 4.24–5.39% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 2.5–5.1% Polyuria: 1.7%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Severe hypoglycemia: 0.6–1.1% Mild hypoglycemia: 9.75–10.37% Vascular disorders: Orthostatic hypotension: 0.4–0.8% Investigations: Percentage change in bone mineral density: -0.9% and -1.0%	A 26-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01106651

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 269, with T2DM and stage 3 chronic kidney disease (CKD), estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) \geq 30 and $<$ 50 ml/min/1.73 m ² , on monotherapy or combined glucose-lowering therapy. HbA1c level at baseline: \geq 7.0 and \leq 10.5% (Yale et al. 2013)	Canagliflozin 100 or 300 mg	Placebo	Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg reduced HbA1c level by: -0.33% and -0.44%. The percentage change in body weight was: -1.6% and -1.8% with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg, corresponding to -1.4 kg and -1.6 kg. Reduction of systolic blood pressure by: -6.1 mmHg and -6.4 mmHg. Reduction of diastolic blood pressure by -2.6 mmHg and -3.5 mmHg. Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg therapy increased HDL-C.	Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 2.2–4.5% Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 5.6–7.9% Genital mycotic infections: Male: 1.7–2.1% Female: 2.4–3.1% Upper respiratory tract infection: 4.49–5.56% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Six patients had severe episodes of hypoglycemia [4 (4.7%), 1 (1.2%), and 1 (1.1%) with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg and placebo]. Vitamin D deficiency: 2.22% and 1.12% Investigations: An increase in serum Magnesium was observed with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg.	52-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01064414
N = 584 with T2DM insufficiently controlled with diet and exercise. HbA1c level at baseline: \geq 7.0 and \leq 10.0% (Stenlöf et al. 2013)	Canagliflozin 100 or 300 mg once daily	Placebo	At week 26, the HbA1c level was significantly reduced with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg: -0.77% and -1.03%. Body weight reduction: -2.2% (-1.9 kg) and -3.3% (-2.9 kg). Reduction of systolic blood pressure at week 26 by: -3.7 and -5.4 mmHg. Diastolic blood pressure reduction by: -1.6 and -2.0 mmHg. Significant increase in HDL-C was observed with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg at week 26: 6.8% and 6.1%.	Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 2.6–3.0% Polyuria: 3.0%. Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 5.1–7.2%; Genital mycotic infections: Male: 2.5–5.6% Female: 7.4–8.8%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented hypoglycemia with Canagliflozin 100 and 300 mg: 3.6% and 3.0% Investigations: Increase of creatinine: 2.8% and 3.5%.	26-week, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01081834

Dapagliflozin

Dapagliflozin has been administered in nine clinical trials, of which six were placebo-controlled and three were placebo- and active-controlled. The duration of these trials was between 16 and 104 weeks, and all were randomized. Six of the clinical trials were 24 weeks in duration. The total number of patients was 4,012. The interventions administered were Dapagliflozin 2.5, 5, and 10 mg. Dapagliflozin was compared with placebo in six of the analyzed trials and with placebo and Metformin 500 mg/day in one trial. In one of the trials, Dapagliflozin (2.5, 5, or 10 mg/day) was added to Glimepiride 4 mg/day. Combination therapy between Dapagliflozin/Saxagliptin/Metformin was studied in one of the trials. Results regarding efficacy for HbA1c reduction show that Dapagliflozin 2.5 mg reduces HbA1c levels by -0.60%, Dapagliflozin 5 mg by -0.68%, and Dapagliflozin 10 mg by -0.70%. We calculated that the reduction in body weight with Dapagliflozin 2.5 mg is by 2.22 kg, with Dapagliflozin 5 mg by 2.47 kg, and with Dapagliflozin 10 mg by 2.67 kg. The mean reduction in systolic blood pressure with Dapagliflozin 5 mg and Dapagliflozin 10 mg is -3.5 mmHg and -5.0 mmHg. The mean decrease in diastolic pressure is by -2.3 mmHg and -3.0 mmHg. The most common adverse events are urinary tract infections, genital mycotic infections, nasopharyngitis, and back pain. A decrease in triglyceride levels, an increase in hematocrit, and a decrease in serum uric acid levels are observed.

Empagliflozin

Empagliflozin has been administered in eight clinical trials, of which six were placebo-controlled and two were placebo- and active-controlled. Their duration was between 12 and 78 weeks, and all were randomized. The total number of patients was 4,199. In seven of the trials, the interventions administered were Empagliflozin 10 mg and 25 mg. In one of the trials, the intervention administered was Empagliflozin 1.5, 10, 25, and 50 mg. In six of the analyzed trials, Empagliflozin was compared with placebo, and in two it was compared with placebo and Sitagliptin 100 mg. The results on efficacy to reduce HbA1c level show that Empagliflozin 10 mg reduces HbA1c levels by -0.66% and Empagliflozin 25 mg by -0.72%. We calculated that the reduction in body weight with Empagliflozin 10 mg is 2.08 kg and with Empagliflozin 25 mg is 2.18 kg. The mean reduction in systolic blood pressure with Empagliflozin 10 mg and Empagliflozin 25 mg is -3.1 mmHg and -5.6 mmHg. The mean reduction in diastolic pressure is by -1.8 mmHg and -3.1 mmHg. The most common adverse events are urinary tract infections, genital mycotic infections, nasopharyngitis, back pain, arthralgia, and headache. An increase in HDL-C levels, an increase in hematocrit, and a decrease in serum uric acid levels are observed. Empagliflozin reduces albuminuria, which is a marker of glomerular damage in patients with CKD.

Table 3. PICOS Dapagliflozin.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardiovascular benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 274, with T2DM, age 18–77 years, with poor glycemic control only with diet and exercise. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.0–10.0%. (Bailey et al. 2015)	Dapagliflozin 2.5 mg (n = 65), 5 mg (n = 64), or 10 mg (n = 70) once daily in the morning	Placebo (n = 75). After 24 weeks, Metformin 500 mg/day was added to the placebo group.	HbA1c level reduction in the Dapagliflozin 2.5, 5, and 10 mg groups at week 24: –0.58%, –0.77%, and –0.89%. Dapagliflozin 5 and 10 mg reduced HbA1c level at week 102 by: –0.53% and –0.44%. Dapagliflozin 5 and 10 mg reduced FPG by: –0.69 mmol/l and –1.12 mmol/l. Body weight reduction: –2.60 kg with Dapagliflozin 10 mg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: At least one hypoglycemic episode: 4.3% with Dapagliflozin 10 mg. Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections: - Male: 8.3, 6.5, and 5.9%. - Female: 13.8, 12.1, and 25.0%; Urinary tract infection: 6.2%, 12.5%, and 8.6% Nasopharyngitis: 16.9, 7.8, and 14.3% Upper respiratory tract infection: 6.15%, 1.56%, and 7.14% Nervous system disorders: Headache: 9.2, 7.8, and 8.6% Investigations: Increased hematocrit: 2.17, 2.28, and 2.80% Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 4.62, 6.25, and 7.14%.	102-week, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT00528372
N = 261 Japanese patients with T2DM, poorly controlled with diet and exercise. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.5%. Most had mild to moderate renal impairment (eGFR: 43–103 ml/min/1.73 m ²). (Kaku et al. 2014)	Dapagliflozin 5 or 10 mg once a day	Placebo	Reduction of HbA1c level: Dapagliflozin (5 mg, –0.41%; 10 mg, –0.45%) at week 24. FPG reduction with Dapagliflozin: (5 mg: –8.6 mg/dL; 10 mg: –13.7 mg/dL). Body weight reduction with Dapagliflozin 5 mg by –2.13 kg; Dapagliflozin 10 mg by –2.22 kg. SBP reduction: Dapagliflozin (5 mg: –3.3 mmHg; 10 mg: –3.2 mmHg).	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 10.47% and 17.05% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 2.3% and 4.5%. Investigations: Triglyceride reduction: 5 mg: –13.65%; 10 mg: –7.84%	24-week, randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, multicenter, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01294423
N = 808, with T2DM poorly controlled with insulin therapy ≥ 30 IU/day, with or without up to two oral glucose-lowering medicinal products. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.5–10.5%. (Wilding et al. 2014)	Dapagliflozin 2.5, 5, or 10 mg/day. At week 48, patients on Dapagliflozin 5 mg therapy switched to therapy with Dapagliflozin 10 mg.	Placebo	HbA1c level reduction at week 104: –0.64, –0.82%, and –0.78% in the Dapagliflozin group. Reduction of body weight at week 104: –2.81 kg, –2.86 kg, and –3.33 kg in the Dapagliflozin 2.5, 5/10-mg, and 10-mg groups. Systolic/diastolic blood pressure decreased by: –2.6/–2.9 mmHg and –7.5/–4.0 mmHg in the Dapagliflozin 5/10 mg and 10 mg groups	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 17.3%, 18.4%, and 16.8%. Urinary tract infection: 5.9%, 9.4%, and 8.7%. Genital mycotic infections: 1.0%, 5.2%, and 5.1%. Upper respiratory tract infection: 4.5%, 6.1%, and 5.6%. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 3.0%, 3.3%, and 5.1%. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 7.4%, 5.7%, and 7.7%. Gastrointestinal disorders: Nausea: 3.5%, 2.8%, and 4.1%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Severe hypoglycemia: 2.0%, 1.4%, and 1.5%.	A 104-week, randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind, multicenter trial followed by two extended periods of 24 and 56 weeks ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT00673231

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardiovascular benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 400, with T2DM, who had insufficient glycemic control despite therapy with Metformin (≥ 1500 mg/day). Baseline HbA1c level: ≥ 6.7 and $\leq 10.5\%$ (Schumm-Draeger et al. 2015)	Dapagliflozin twice daily (2.5 or 5 mg) or Dapagliflozin 10 mg once daily. Metformin therapy continued during the trial.	Placebo	Mean decrease in HbA1c level in Dapagliflozin 2.5 and 5 mg twice daily groups: -0.52% and -0.65% . For Dapagliflozin 10 mg once daily, the decrease in the HbA1c level was -0.59% . Average change in FPG: -20.8 , -25.6 , and 20.4 mg/dL. Weight reduction with Dapagliflozin 10 mg once daily: -2.76% or -1.73 kg. Weight reduction with Dapagliflozin 2.5 and 5 mg twice a day: -1.62 kg and -1.88 kg. All groups taking Dapagliflozin showed a decrease in systolic blood pressure.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 2% Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 2.0%, 5.0%, and 3.0% Genital infection: 5.0% and 3.0% Influenza: 5.0% for Dapagliflozin 2.5 mg and 2.0% for Dapagliflozin 10 mg.	A 16-week, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01217892
N = 597 with uncontrolled T2DM despite monotherapy with a sulphonylurea. HbA1c level at baseline: 7–10%. (Strojek et al. 2011)	Dapagliflozin (2.5, 5, or 10 mg/day) added to Glimepiride 4 mg/day	Placebo added to Glimepiride 4 mg/day	HbA1c level reduction with Dapagliflozin 2.5/5/10 mg was -0.58 , -0.63 , and -0.82% . Body weight reduction by -1.18 kg, -1.56 kg, and -2.26 kg. FPG decreased by: -0.93 , -1.18 , and -1.58 mmol/l. All doses of Dapagliflozin are associated with a moderate reduction of systolic blood pressure.	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 1.9%, 5.5%, 3.3% Upper respiratory tract infection: 3.2%, 4.1%, and 4.6%. Genital mycotic infection: 3.9%, 6.2%, and 6.6%. Urinary tract infection: 3.9%, 6.9%, and 5.3%. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 1.9%, 2.1%, and 4.6%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: One or more hypoglycemic events: 7.1%, 6.9%, and 7.9%. Investigations: -Slightly elevated hematocrit: 1.93%, 2.28%, and 2.19%. -Serum uric acid decrease: -21.41 , -26.17 , and -26.17 $\mu\text{mol/l}$	24-week, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, international, multicenter trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT00680745
N = 546, with T2DM and poor glycemic control, on therapy with Metformin (≥ 1500 mg daily). HbA1c level at baseline: 7–10%. (Bailey et al. 2010)	Dapagliflozin (2.5 mg, n = 137; 5 mg, n = 137, or 10 mg, n = 135) orally daily. Patients continued to take the dose of Metformin they had taken prior to the trial.	Placebo (n = 137)	At week 24, mean HbA1c level decreased by -0.67% in the Dapagliflozin 2.5 mg group, -0.70% in the Dapagliflozin 5 mg group, and -0.84% in the Dapagliflozin 10 mg group. Body weight reduction: -2.2 , -3.0 , and -2.9 kg. Increase in HDL cholesterol: 1.8–4.4% Reduction of systolic blood pressure by: -2.1 , -4.3 , and -5.1 mmHg	Nervous system disorders: Headache: 3%, 7%, and 8%. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 8.03%, 5.11%, and 13.33%. Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 3%, 5%, and 11.8%. Genital mycotic infection: 8%, 13%, and 9%. Nasopharyngitis: 9%, 3%, and 6%. Influenza: 13.87%, 14.6%, and 12.59%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 2%, 4%, and 4%. Investigations: Serum uric acid reduction ($\mu\text{mol/L}$): -30.9 , -36.3 , and -47.6 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ Hematocrit increase: 1.0%, 1.3%, and 1.7% Reduction in triglyceride level by: -2.4% , -6.2% , and -6.2%	24-week randomized, multicenter, double-blind, parallel-group, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT00528879

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardiovascular benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 485 patients with T2DM, aged 18–77 years. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.0–10% (Ferrannini et al. 2010)	Dapagliflozin 2.5, 5, or 10 mg once a day in the morning or in the evening. Patients with an HbA1c level of 10.1–12% were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive treatment with a morning dose of Dapagliflozin 5 or 10 mg/day.	Placebo	The mean change in HbA1c at week 24 was: –0.58%, –0.77%, and –0.89% with Dapagliflozin 2.5, 5, and 10 mg. In patients with a baseline HbA1c level of 9%, the change in mean HbA1c at week 24 was: –1.23%, –1.98%, and –1.90% in the Dapagliflozin 2.5, 5, and 10 mg groups. . Body weight reduction by: –3.3, –2.8, and –3.2 kg. Systolic blood pressure decreased by: –3.6 and –4.6 mmHg. Diastolic blood pressure decreased by: –2.8, –1.7, and –2.0 mmHg.	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 10.8, 4.7 and 2.9% Urinary tract infection: 4.6, 12.5, and 5.7% Genital mycotic infections: 7.7, 7.8, and 12.9% Gastrointestinal disorders: Diarrhea: 6.2, 1.6, and 1.4% Nervous system disorders: Headache: 7.7, 4.7, and 5.7% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 1.5–2.9% Investigations: Reduction of serum creatinine by: –0.6, –2.0, and –1.1 µmol/L Serum uric acid decreased by: –39.3 to –51.7 µmol/L Hematocrit increased by: 1.60, 1.74, and 2.38%	24-week randomized, parallel-group, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT00528372
N = 321, with T2DM and chronic kidney disease [CKD] stage 3A (eGFR: 45–59 ml/min/1.73 m ²). HbA1c level at baseline: 7.0%–11.0%. (Fioretto et al. 2018)	Dapagliflozin 10 mg	Placebo	HbA1c level reduction: –0.37% with Dapagliflozin 10 mg. Body weight reduction at week 24: –3.17 kg with Dapagliflozin 10 mg. Reduction of FPG by –1.2 mmol/L with Dapagliflozin 10 mg. Reduction of SBP by –4.8 mmHg with Dapagliflozin 10 mg.	Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections: 1.9% Urinary tract infection: 2.5% Vascular disorders: Hypotension: 1.9% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemic events: 12.5%. Investigations: Reduction of serum uric acid: –11.9 µmol/L	24-week randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, placebo-controlled phase 3 trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02413398
N = 320 with T2DM and poor glycemic control. Group A patients had an HbA1c level of 8.0–11.5%. These patients were treated with Metformin 500 mg and Saxagliptin 5 mg/day for 16 weeks. Patients in group B had an HbA1c level of 7.5–10.5%. These patients were treated with Metformin 500 mg and Saxagliptin 5 mg/day for 8 weeks. (Mathieu et al. 2015)	Dapagliflozin 10 mg once daily + Saxagliptin + Metformin	Placebo + Saxagliptin + Metformin	HbA1c level reduction in the Dapa+Saxa+Met arm: –0.82% HbA1c level reduction in the Pla+Saxa+Met arm: –0.1% The change in FPG level for the Dapa+Saxa+Met arm was 32.7 mg/dL The Dapa+Saxa+Met arm weight reduction was with –1.91 kg 36.7% of patients achieved an HbA1c level of < 7.0% Change in systolic blood pressure –1.9 mmHg and in diastolic pressure –1.7 mmHg in the arm on therapy with Dapa+Saxa+Met.	Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 9.38% Nasopharyngitis: 3.13% Genital mycotic infections: 4.38% Nervous system disorders: Headache: 6.88% Gastrointestinal disorders: Diarrhea: 4.38% Nausea: 2.50% Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 3.13% Arthralgia: 2.50% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Dyslipidemia: 4.38%	24-week, multicenter, randomized, placebo-controlled, parallel-group, phase 3 trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01646320

Table 4. PICOS Empagliflozin.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 495, with T2DM inadequately controlled with Metformin. HbA1c baseline: >7 to ≤10%. (Rosenstock et al. 2013)	Empagliflozin 1, 5, 10, 25, or 50 mg once daily (QD) added to Metformin for 12 weeks.	Placebo or Sitagliptin 100 mg once daily	HbA1c level reduction at week 12: -0.09, -0.23, -0.56, -0.55 and -0.49% with Empagliflozin; -0.45% reduction with Sitagliptin 100 mg. Body weight reduction with: -1.6, -2.3, -2.7, -2.6, and -2.9 kg. Changes in systolic blood pressure: -2.17, -3.03, -4.39, -8.51, and -3.16 mmHg. Change in diastolic pressure: -0.06, -0.75, -1.70, -4.16 and -1.99 mmHg	Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 2.8–5.7% Genital mycotic infections: 1.4–9.9% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 1.4–4.3% Nervous system disorders: Headache: 1.4–4.2% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 1.4–4.2% Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 1.4–2.9%.	12-week, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT00749190
N = 741, with T2DM and chronic kidney disease (CKD) stage 2 (eGFR ≥60 to <90 ml/min per 1.73 m ²). Patients with stage 3 CKD (eGFR ≥30 to <60 ml/min per 1.73 m ²). HbA1c level at baseline: 7%–10%. (Barnett et al. 2014)	Empagliflozin 10 mg or 25 mg once daily	Placebo	In patients with stage 2 CKD, the HbA1c level reduction at week 24 was by -0.52% with Empagliflozin 10 mg and -0.68% with Empagliflozin 25 mg. In patients with stage 3 CKD, the mean change in HbA1c at week 24 was by -0.42% for Empagliflozin 25 mg. Body weight reduction with: -1.76 and -2.33 kg at week 24 and -2.0 and -2.6 kg at week 52 with Empagliflozin 10 mg or 25 mg. Change in systolic blood pressure: -1.7 and -6.2 mmHg. Change in diastolic pressure: -1.2 and -3.0 mmHg. Empagliflozin reduced albuminuria, which is a marker for glomerular damage. More patients with stage 3 CKD on therapy with Empagliflozin 25 mg had an improvement from macroalbuminuria at baseline to microalbuminuria.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 24.7%, 28.9%, and 37.8% in stage 2, 3, and 4 CKD. Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 9.3, 13.4, and 18.9% Genital mycotic infections: 2.7–5.2% Upper respiratory tract infection: 13.4, 10.2, and 8.1% Nasopharyngitis: 13.4, 4.8, and 13.5%. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 9.3, 4.3, and 5.4% with Empagliflozin 25 mg. Gastrointestinal disorders: Nausea: 3.1, 4.3, and 13.5%	52-week, randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, placebo-controlled trial at 127 centers in 15 countries NCT01164501
N = 637, with T2DM on therapy with Metformin (≥1500 mg/day). Baseline HbA1c level: ≥7% to ≤10%. (Häring et al. 2014)	Empagliflozin 10 mg (n = 217), Empagliflozin 25 mg (n = 213) once daily	Placebo (n = 207)	HbA1c level reduction at week 24: -0.70% with Empagliflozin 10 mg and -0.77% with Empagliflozin 25 mg. Body weight reduction: -1.63 kg with Empagliflozin 10 mg and -2.01 kg with Empagliflozin 25 mg. The average reduction at week 24 in SBP and DBP was with -2.44 mmHg and -3.6 mmHg. 36.2% of the patients managed to achieve good blood pressure control (130/80 mmHg) at week 24. There was a slight increase in HDL cholesterol.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Confirmed hypoglycemic events were reported in 0.5%, 1.8%, and 1.4% of patients receiving placebo, Empagliflozin 10 mg and 25 mg, respectively. Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 5.1% and 5.6% Genital mycotic infections: 3.7% and 4.7%. Nasopharyngitis: 5.5–7.0% Upper respiratory tract infection: 0.92% and 4.21%	24-week, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01159600

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N=494, with poorly controlled T2DM, on basal insulin therapy. Mean HbA1c level at baseline: 8.2% BMI: 32.2 kg/m ² .	Empagliflozin 10 mg (n = 169), Empagliflozin 25 mg (n = 155)	Placebo (n = 170)	HbA1c level reduction at week 18: -0.6 ± 0.1% with Empagliflozin 10 mg and -0.7 ± 0.1% with Empagliflozin 25 mg. Body weight reduction: with Empagliflozin 10 mg (-1.7 ± 0.6 kg) and with Empagliflozin 25 mg (-0.9 ± 0.6 kg). Changes in systolic blood pressure: -3.7 ± 0.9 mmHg with Empagliflozin 10 mg and -3.3 ± 1.0 mmHg with Empagliflozin 25 mg. At week 78, the change in HbA1c level was: -0.5 ± 0.1% with Empagliflozin 10 mg and -0.6 ± 0.1% with Empagliflozin 25 mg. Body weight reduction by -2.2 ± 0.5 kg with Empagliflozin 10 mg and -2.0 ± 0.5 kg with Empagliflozin 25 mg. Changes in systolic blood pressure with Empagliflozin 10 mg: -4.1 ± 1.0 mmHg. Changes in diastolic pressure with Empagliflozin 10 mg: -2.9 ± 0.7 mmHg	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Confirmed hypoglycemic events with Empagliflozin 10 mg and with Empagliflozin 25 mg: 33.14% and 36%. Infections and Infestations: Urinary tract infection: Empagliflozin 10 mg (15%), Empagliflozin 25 mg (12%). Genital mycotic infections: 8% and 5% in the Empagliflozin 10 and 25 mg groups. Nasopharyngitis: 12% and 11%. Upper respiratory tract infection: 10.65% and 8.39%. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 7% and 8%. Arthralgia: 4% and 5%. Psychiatric disorders: Depression: 7% and 1%. Gastrointestinal disorders: Diarrhea: 6% and 7%. Nausea: 5%	78-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01011868
(Rosenstock et al. 2015)					
N = 899, aged ≥18 years who had not received oral or injectable glucose-lowering therapy in the previous 12 weeks. HbA1c level at baseline: 7-10%.	Empagliflozin 10 mg, once daily Empagliflozin 25 mg once daily	Placebo or Sitagliptin 100 mg once a day	HbA1c level reduction: -0.74%, -0.85%, and -0.73% with Empagliflozin 10 mg, 25 mg, and Sitagliptin. Body weight reduction with: -2.26 and -2.48 kg with Empagliflozin 10 and 25 mg and weight gain of +0.18 kg with Sitagliptin 100 mg. In patients with blood pressure ≥130/80 mm Hg, changes in systolic pressure were: -3.9 mmHg with Empagliflozin 10 mg and -5.0 mmHg with Empagliflozin 25 mg.	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 7%, 5%, and 7% with Empagliflozin 10/25 mg and Sitagliptin 100 mg. Urinary tract infection: 6%, 4%, and 5%, more common for female patients. 3% reported genital mycotic infection in the Empagliflozin 10 mg group, 4% in the Empagliflozin 25 mg group. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: <1% for both doses of Empagliflozin. Dyslipidemia: 6%, 4%, and 3%. Investigations: HDL-cholesterol increased significantly from baseline in patients treated with Empagliflozin 10 mg or 25 mg. Slight increase in hematocrit and slight decrease in serum uric acid in the Empagliflozin groups.	24-week, multicenter, randomized, double-blind placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01177813
(Roden et al. 2013)					

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
<p>N = 498, with T2DM aged 18–65 years, BMI 45 kg/m², on monotherapy with Pioglitazone 30 mg/day (122) or Pioglitazone in combination with Metformin 1500 mg/day (376).</p> <p>Baseline HbA1c level: 7%–10%.</p> <p>A total of 305 patients (61.2%) were treated in the initial 24-week trial and participated in the extended trial period. (Kovacs et al. 2015)</p>	<p>Empagliflozin 10 mg or 25 mg once daily as adjunctive therapy to Pioglitazone with or without Metformin</p>	<p>Placebo once a day</p>	<p>HbA1c level reduction at week 76: –0.59% with Empagliflozin 10 mg and –0.69% with Empagliflozin 25 mg.</p> <p>Body weight reduction at week 76: –2.0 kg and –1.7 kg with Empagliflozin 10 mg and 25 mg.</p> <p>Decrease in SBP: –2.0 and –3.7 mmHg, and in DBP with –1.5 and –2.2 mmHg with Empagliflozin 10 mg and 25 mg.</p>	<p>Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Confirmed hypoglycemic events were reported in higher share in the placebo group (4.2%) than in the Empagliflozin 10 mg (1.8%) or 25 mg (3.0%) group. Dyslipidemia: 13.9% and 12.5%.</p> <p>Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 26.7% of patients in the placebo group, 22.4% in the Empagliflozin 10 mg group, and 22.0% in the Empagliflozin group 25 mg. Genital mycotic infection: 3.0%, 10.3%, and 4.2% of the placebo, Empagliflozin 10 mg and Empagliflozin 25 mg groups. Nasopharyngitis: 6.1% and 5.4% Upper respiratory tract infection: 5.5% and 8.9%</p> <p>Investigations: Slight increase in hematocrit and decrease in serum uric acid was observed with Empagliflozin. Increase in HDL-C in the Empagliflozin 10 mg group.</p> <p>Blood and lymphatic system disorders: Anemia: 4.2% and 6.5%</p> <p>Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 6.1% and 4.2% Arthralgia: 6.7% and 6.0%</p> <p>Nervous system disorders: Headaches: 6.1% and 7.7%</p>	<p>76-week, randomized, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01210001</p>
<p>N = 269 Japanese patients with T2DM, insufficiently controlled with insulin therapy—dose 31.4 IU/day.</p> <p>Baseline HbA1c level: ≥ 7.5%–≤ 10.0%. (Sone et al. 2020)</p>	<p>Empagliflozin 10 mg (n = 89), Empagliflozin 25 mg (n = 90)</p>	<p>Placebo (n = 90)</p>	<p>HbA1c level reduction at week 16: –0.92% and –1.00% with Empagliflozin 10 mg or 25 mg.</p> <p>Body weight reduction with Empagliflozin 10 mg and Empagliflozin 25 mg: –1.79 kg and –1.74 kg.</p> <p>Reduction of HbA1c level at week 52: –0.89 and –0.95%.</p> <p>Body weight reduction with Empagliflozin 10 mg and Empagliflozin 25 mg at week 52: –1.78 and –1.92 kg.</p> <p>At week 52, the changes in systolic blood pressure were: –2.25 and –4.82 mmHg</p>	<p>Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 20.9% and 24.4% in the Empagliflozin 10 mg or 25 mg groups.</p> <p>Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 5.8%, 6.7%, and 8.9% in the Empagliflozin 10 mg, 25 mg, and placebo groups. Genital mycotic infections: 3.5%, 3.3%, and 0% of the participants in the Empagliflozin 10 mg, 25 mg, and placebo groups. Nasopharyngitis: 34.88% and 26.67%</p> <p>Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 10.5% and 10.0%</p> <p>Investigations: A slight increase in the levels of vitamin D and parathyroid hormone. Slight increase in ketone bodies: 5.81% and 2.22%.</p> <p>Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 5.8 and 6.7%</p>	<p>52-week, randomized, multicenter, double-blind, parallel-group trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02589639</p>

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 166 African Americans with poorly controlled T2DM and arterial hypertension. 52.7% of participants were male, with an average age of 56.8 years; and an average duration of T2DM of 9.3 years. HbA1c level at baseline: 8.59%; Ambulatory systolic blood pressure: 146.3 mmHg; ambulatory diastolic blood pressure, 89.4 mmHg. (Ferdinand et al. 2019)	Empagliflozin 10 mg or Empagliflozin 25 mg	Placebo	Decrease in HbA1c level with Empagliflozin 10–25 mg: –0.71%. Body weight reduction at week 24 with Empagliflozin 10–25 mg: –2.21 kg. Change from baseline to week 24 of the average 24-hour outpatient SBP: –10.33 mmHg with Empagliflozin 10–25 mg. Change from baseline to week 24 of the average 24-hour ambulatory DBP: –6.38 mmHg with Empagliflozin 10–25 mg.	Infections and infestations: Upper respiratory tract infection: 2.50% Urinary tract infection: 5% Genital mycotic infection: 11.1% in women Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 3.8% Investigations: Increased lipase: 7.50% The level of serum uric acid decreased by ≈15%. Increase in hematocrit by an average of 2.4% in the Empagliflozin group. No cases of ketoacidosis have been reported.	24-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02182830

Ertugliflozin

Ertugliflozin has been administered in seven clinical trials, of which four were placebo-controlled, one was active-controlled, and two were placebo- and active-controlled. They lasted between 26 and 104 weeks, and all were randomized. The total number of patients was 4,460. The interventions administered were Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg. In four of the analyzed trials, Ertugliflozin was compared with placebo, in one it was compared with Glimepiride, and in two it was compared with placebo and Metformin or placebo and Glimepiride. Results regarding efficacy for HbA1c reduction show that Ertugliflozin 5 mg reduces HbA1c levels by –0.8% and Ertugliflozin 15 mg by –0.9%. We calculated that the reduction in body weight with Ertugliflozin 5 mg is by 2.85 kg and with Ertugliflozin 15 mg is by 2.93 kg. The mean reduction in systolic blood pressure with Ertugliflozin 5 mg and Ertugliflozin 15 mg is by –3.0 mmHg and –4.0 mmHg. The mean reduction in diastolic pressure is by –2.4 mmHg. The most common adverse events are urinary tract infections, genital mycotic infections, polyuria, pollakiuria, and hypovolemia. There is an increase in HDL-C level, an increase in hematocrit, and a decrease in serum uric acid levels. Minimal changes in bone mineral density are observed. A fracture is reported in one of the analyzed clinical trials.

Ipragliflozin

Ipragliflozin has been administered in three clinical trials, all three of which were placebo-controlled. Their duration was 24 weeks, and all were randomized. The total number of patients was 472. The intervention administered was Ipragliflozin 50 mg, administered in two of the trials as adjunctive therapy to Metformin and in one as adjunctive therapy to Metformin and Sitagliptin. The results regarding efficacy in reducing HbA1c levels show that administration of Ipragliflozin 50 mg results in a mean

reduction by –0.88%. We calculated that the body weight reduction with Ipragliflozin 50 mg to be 2.1 kg. The mean reduction of systolic and diastolic blood pressure with Ipragliflozin 50 mg is –1.65 mmHg and –1.24 mmHg, respectively. The most common adverse events are urinary tract infection, nasopharyngitis, and pollakiuria. There is an increase in HDL-C levels, an increase in hematocrit, and a decrease in triglyceride levels. In one of the clinical trials, a decrease in the levels of the liver enzymes AST (aspartate aminotransferase) and ALT (alanine aminotransferase) is also reported.

Bexagliflozin

Bexagliflozin has been administered in five clinical trials, three of which were placebo-controlled and two were active-controlled. Their duration was between 24 and 96 weeks, and all were randomized. The total number of patients was 3,141. The intervention administered was Bexagliflozin 20 mg, and in three of the trials it was compared with placebo (in one of these it was administered as adjunctive therapy to Metformin), in one it was compared with Sitagliptin 100 mg, again as adjunctive therapy to Metformin, and in one it was compared with Glimepiride 2, 4, or 6 mg once daily. The results on efficacy to reduce HbA1c level show that administration of Bexagliflozin 20 mg results in a mean HbA1c reduction by –0.81%. We calculated that the reduction in body weight with Bexagliflozin 20 mg to be –2.49 kg. The mean reduction in systolic blood pressure with Bexagliflozin 20 mg is by –4.0 mmHg. The most common adverse events are urinary tract infection, genital mycotic infection, nasopharyngitis, polyuria, and pollakiuria. Fractures are reported in two of the trials. There is an increase in HDL-C, an increase in hematocrit, and a decrease in triglyceride and serum uric acid levels.

The assessment of the primary endpoints based on the conducted PICOS analysis is graphically presented in Figs 2, 3.

Table 5. PICOS Ertugliflozin.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 506 Asian patients with T2DM, poorly controlled only with Metformin therapy. Baseline characteristics: BMI \geq 18.0 kg/m ² . HbA1c level: 7.0–10.5%. (Ji et al. 2019)	Ertugliflozin 5 or 15 mg + Metformin (\geq 1500 mg/day)	Placebo	HbA1c level reduction with Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg: –1.0%, –0.9% HbA1c level <6.5% up to week 26: Ertugliflozin 5 mg (14.7%) and 15 mg (15.4%). Body weight reduction by: –1.8 kg and –2.0 kg. Change in systolic blood pressure: –5.1 and –3.9 mmHg. Change in diastolic pressure: –2.38 and –2.36 mmHg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Documented hypoglycemia: 6.5% and 8.3%. Symptomatic hypoglycemia: 2.4% and 4.7% Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections: 2.7% and 1.4% Urinary tract infection: 1.8% and 1.2% Nasopharyngitis: 5.29% and 5.33% Upper respiratory tract infection: 2.35% and 5.33%.	26 weeks, randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02630706
N = 461, with poorly controlled T2DM despite appropriate diet and exercise. They were included in phase A of the trial; baseline HbA1c level: 7.0%–10.5%. 384 patients participated in phase B and received \geq 1 dose of the investigational medicinal product. (Aronson et al. 2018)	Ertugliflozin 5 mg/day or Ertugliflozin 15 mg/day	Phase A, during which 461 participants received a placebo. Phase B, during which participants in the placebo group were given Metformin.	At week 52, the change in HbA1c level was with –0.9% and –1.0% in the Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg groups. The proportion of participants with HbA1c level <7.0% at week 52 was: 25.6% and 28.5%. Change in FPG from baseline to week 52 was: –1.6 mmol/L, –1.6 mmol/L, and –1.8 mmol/L in the placebo/Metformin, Ertugliflozin 5 mg, and Ertugliflozin 15 mg group. At week 52, the reduction in body weight was with: –3.3 kg and –3.6 kg. The reduction of SBP was by: –3.7 mmHg and –1.8 mmHg.	Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections in women on therapy with Ertugliflozin 5 mg (26.9%) and Ertugliflozin 15 mg (29.0%). Urinary tract infection: 10.9% in the Ertugliflozin 5 mg group and 6.6% in the Ertugliflozin 15 mg group. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: The incidence of symptomatic hypoglycemia was lower in the Ertugliflozin groups (5 mg—1.3%; 15 mg—2.6%) compared to the placebo/Metformin group (4.6%). Vascular disorders: Hypovolemia: 4.6%, 1.9%, and 2.0%, respectively, for placebo/Metformin, Ertugliflozin 5 mg, and Ertugliflozin 15 mg. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Polyuria: 1.9% and 1.3% Pollakiuria: 3.2 and 2.0% Investigations: Reduction in serum uric acid from baseline at week 52 in both groups of Ertugliflozin. Average increase from baseline in hemoglobin and hematocrit levels.	52-week, multicenter, randomized trial consisting of a 26-week, double-blind, placebo-controlled period (Phase A). Followed by a 26-week active-controlled period (Phase B). ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01958671
N = 464, with T2DM, poorly controlled with Metformin \geq 1500 mg/day and Sitagliptin 100 mg/day. Baseline characteristics: HbA1c: 7.0%–10%. eGFR \geq 60 ml/min/1.73 m ² . (Dagogo-Jack et al. 2018)	Ertugliflozin 5 mg once daily or Ertugliflozin 15 mg once daily	Placebo	After 26 weeks, the change in HbA1c level was with –0.75% and –0.81% with Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg. 17.0%, 32.1%, and 39.9% of the patients receiving placebo, Ertugliflozin 5 mg, or Ertugliflozin 15 mg achieved an HbA1c level of <7.0%. The reduction of body weight with Ertugliflozin was: –3.5 kg and –2.8 kg. The change in systolic blood pressure was with: –4.2 mmHg and –4.1 mmHg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: The incidence of symptomatic hypoglycemia and documented hypoglycemia was low: placebo: 3.3%, Ertugliflozin 5 mg: 4.5%, Ertugliflozin 15 mg: 2.0%. At the 52nd week placebo: 7.2%, Ertugliflozin 5 mg: 5.1%, Ertugliflozin 15 mg: 5.2%. Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: placebo: 3.3%; Ertugliflozin 5 mg: 5.1%; Ertugliflozin 15 mg: 3.9%. Urinary tract infection: placebo: 5.2%; Ertugliflozin 5 mg: 1.3%; Ertugliflozin 15 mg: 3.3%. Genital mycotic infections in women: 12.0% and 14.1%. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 5.13% and 1.96%.	52-week, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02036515

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 461, aged ≥18 years with poor glycemic control despite diet and exercise. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.0%–10.5%. (Terra et al. 2017)	Ertugliflozin 5 mg or Ertugliflozin 15 mg	Placebo	At the 26th week, the mean HbA1c level reduction was: –0.99% and –1.16% with Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg. At week 26, the reduction in body weight was by –1.76 kg and –2.16 kg with Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg. Decrease in SBP at week 26 by –3.93 mmHg in the Ertugliflozin 15 mg group. Decrease in DBP by: –1.80 mmHg and –0.37 mmHg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: Constipation: 6.4% and 0.7% of patients on therapy with Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg. Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections in women: 16.4% and 22.6% in the Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg group; in men: 3.4% and 5.6% in the Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg groups. Urinary tract infection in the Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg groups: 7.1% and 3.9%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Few patients have had symptomatic hypoglycemia: Ertugliflozin 5 mg (1.3%) and Ertugliflozin 15 mg (2.6%). Vascular disorders: The incidence of hypovolemia in the Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg groups was 1.3% and 2.0%, respectively. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 1.9–2.0% Polyuria: 1.9 and 1.9%	52-week, double-blind, multicenter, randomized, parallel-group trial, with 26-week placebo-controlled period (phase A), followed by 26-week active-controlled period (phase B) ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01958671
N = 621, with T2DM, poorly controlled with Metformin therapy. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.0%–10.5% after at least 8 weeks of therapy with Metformin. (Gallo et al. 2019)	Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg	Phase A: Placebo Phase B: Glimepiride was added to the placebo in participants with FPG ≥6.1 mmol/L.	Mean HbA1c level reduction: –0.70% and –1.0% at week 52; –0.60% and –0.9% at week 104 in the Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg groups. Body weight reduction by: –3.77 kg and –3.63 kg per week 104. Change in systolic blood pressure: –3.61 mmHg and –3.13 mmHg with Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg. Change in diastolic blood pressure: –2.36 mmHg and –1.52 mmHg with Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: The incidence of documented hypoglycemia was: 13.5% and 14.1% with Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg. In 1 participant in the Ertugliflozin 15 mg group was reported diabetic ketoacidosis Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections were more common in women than in men: 7.3% and 9.8%. Urinary tract infection: 4.3% and 10.7% Vascular disorders: Hypovolemia: 2.4% Investigations: Changes in bone mineral density (BMD) of the hip joint, where the percentage reduction in BMD was greater with Ertugliflozin 15 mg compared to placebo/Glimepiride: –0.50% at week 52 and –0.84% at week 104.	104-week, randomized, double-blind trial with 26-week placebo-controlled period (phase A) and an active-controlled 78-week period (phase B). ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02033889
N = 1326, with T2DM who had poor glycemic control on Metformin therapy ≥ 1500 mg/day. Baseline HbA1c level: ≥7.0%–≤9.0%. (Hollander et al. 2018)	Ertugliflozin 15 or 5 mg once a day	Glimepiride (starting dose 1 mg daily, titrated up to 8 mg daily)	At week 52, the mean change in HbA1c was: –0.64%, –0.56%, and –0.74% in the Ertugliflozin 15 mg, Ertugliflozin 5 mg and Glimepiride groups. The average change in body weight at week 52 was: –3.4 kg, –3.0 kg, and 0.9 kg in the Ertugliflozin 15 mg, Ertugliflozin 5 mg, and Glimepiride groups. The average changes in systolic blood pressure at week 52 were: –3.8 mmHg, –2.2 mmHg in the Ertugliflozin 15 mg and 5 mg groups.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Severe hypoglycemia was reported in 0.2%, 0.2%, and 2.3% of participants in the Ertugliflozin 15 mg, Ertugliflozin 5 mg, and Glimepiride groups. Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections were more common in women: 7.7% and 10%. Urinary tract infection: 6.4%–6.7% Vascular disorders: Hypovolemia: 0.7%–1.3% Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Four fractures have been reported: two in patients receiving Ertugliflozin 15 mg, one in a patient receiving Ertugliflozin 5 mg, and one in a patient receiving Glimepiride therapy. Investigations: A greater increase from baseline in HDL-C at week 52 was observed in the Ertugliflozin groups.	52-week, double-blind, randomized, active-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01999218

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 621, with T2DM who had poor glycemic control on therapy with Metformin at least 8 weeks prior to the start of the clinical trial. HbA1c level at baseline: 7.0–10.5%. Mean systolic pressure: 130 mmHg. (Rosenstock et al. 2018)	Ertugliflozin 5 mg or Ertugliflozin 15 mg	Placebo (Glimepiride has been used as a rescue therapy at a dose of 6 or 8 mg per day)	Decrease in HbA1c level: –0.73% with Ertugliflozin 5 mg and –0.91% with Ertugliflozin 15 mg. The reduction in body weight at week 26 was by –2.93 kg and –3.01 kg with Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg. Change in systolic blood pressure: –4.38 and –5.20 mmHg with Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg. Change in diastolic blood pressure: –1.59 and –2.19 mmHg with Ertugliflozin 5 and 15 mg. Percentage of patients with HbA1c level < 7%: 35.3–40%	Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 2.9–8.29% Upper respiratory tract infection: 10.24–11.11% Genital mycotic infections: 5.50–6.30% in women and 3.1–3.2% in men Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 4.35–9.76% Arthralgia: 3.38–5.37% Nervous system disorders: Headache: 5.37–6.76% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 6.76–8.78%	26-week, randomized, double-blind, multicenter, placebo-controlled trial with a 78-week extended period ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02033889

Table 6. PICOS Ipragliflozin.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 165, aged ≥18 years with T2DM, treated with Metformin 1500 mg/day for 12 weeks. Baseline characteristics: HbA1c level: 7.5%–11.0%. BMI: 20–45 kg/m ² . (Shestakova et al. 2018) (Astellas Pharma Inc 2016)	Ipragliflozin 50 mg/day, titrated up to 100 mg/day. They also continued taking Metformin.	Placebo	HbA1c level reduction from baseline to the end of period I: –1.0 ± 0.9% in the Ipragliflozin group and 0.8 ± 1.1% in the placebo group. Body weight reduction in the Ipragliflozin group: –2.01 ± 2.47 kg. Change in systolic blood pressure: –1.4 mmHg. Systolic blood pressure decreased from week 12 to the end of period II in patients, who took Ipragliflozin 100 mg: average change from week 12: –3.1 mmHg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: Ipragliflozin: 11.8%; placebo: 10.9%) Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: Ipragliflozin: 0.0%; placebo: 1.8% Genital mycotic infection: Ipragliflozin: 0.9%; placebo: 0.0%.	24-week double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial consisting of period I [week 0–12] and period II [week 12–24]. ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02794792 1941-CL-9001
N = 139, with T2DM, aged 19–74 years. They were on a low-carb diet ≥8 weeks prior to the start of the trial. They took Metformin ≥1500 mg/day and Sitagliptin 100 mg/day at least 8 weeks prior to the start of the trial. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.0%–10.5%; BMI: 20.0–45.0 kg/m ² (Han et al. 2018) (Astellas Pharma Inc 2015)	Ipragliflozin 50 mg/day as an adjunctive therapy to Metformin and Sitagliptin	Placebo	HbA1c level reduction: –0.79% with Ipragliflozin. Body weight reduction: –1.96 kg. Reduction of systolic blood pressure by: –2.35 mmHg. Decrease in diastolic blood pressure by: –1.49 mmHg.	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 4.1% Urinary tract infection: 2.7% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria and polyuria: 1.4% Investigations: -Increased HDL-C -Reduction of triglycerides. -Increase in hematocrit. -Decrease of AST and ALT. Skin and subcutaneous tissue disorders: Urticaria: 4.1%	24-week, double-blind, randomized, parallel-group, placebo-controlled, multicenter trial conducted in Korea ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02452632 1941-CL-2009

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 168, aged ≥ 20 years with T2DM (diagnosed ≥ 12 weeks ago). They were on therapy with Metformin (≥ 6 weeks). Baseline HbA1c level: 7.4–9.9%. BMI: 20.0–45.0 kg/m ²	Ipragliflozin 50 mg + Metformin therapy	Placebo	HbA1c level reduction: –0.87% Body weight reduction: –2.33 kg. FPG reduction: –1.23 mmol/L. Reduction of systolic blood pressure by –1.2 mmHg and of diastolic blood pressure by –1.0 mmHg.	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 25.9% Upper respiratory tract infection: 3.6% Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 5.4% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 5.4% Cystitis: 1.8% Gastrointestinal disorders: Constipation: 4.5% Nausea and vomiting: 2.7% Nervous system disorders: Headache: 3.6% Investigations: Triglyceride level reduction HDL-C increase	24-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT01135433 1941-CL-0106
(Kashiwagi et al. 2015) (Astellas Pharma Inc 2010)					

The summarized results of the PICOS analysis show that the most significant decrease in HbA1c level is observed after administration of Ertugliflozin 15 mg (–0.90%), Ipragliflozin 50 mg (–0.88%), and Canagliflozin 300 mg (–0.84%). A moderate decrease is observed after administration of Bexagliflozin 20 mg (–0.81%), Ertugliflozin 5 mg (–0.80%), Canagliflozin 100 mg (–0.73%), Empagliflozin 25 mg (–0.72%), and Dapagliflozin 10 mg (–0.70%). The lowest change in HbA1c level is observed after administration of Dapagliflozin 5 mg (–0.68%), Empagliflozin 10 mg (–0.66%), and Dapagliflozin 2.5 mg (–0.60%).

The summarized results of the PICOS analysis show that body weight reduction is most significant after administration of Ertugliflozin 15 mg by –2.93 kg and after administration of Canagliflozin 300 mg by –2.9 kg. The lowest reduction occurs after administration of Empagliflozin 10 mg by –2.08 kg.

Discussion

Yale and Bakris evaluated the efficacy and safety of Canagliflozin in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and stage 3 chronic kidney disease (CKD) with an estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) ≥ 30 and < 50 mL/min/1.73 m². A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled phase 3 clinical trial was conducted, in which 269 participants received therapy with Canagliflozin 100 mg, Canagliflozin 300 mg, or placebo. The primary efficacy endpoint was the change in HbA1c level from baseline at week 26. Pre-specified secondary endpoints included change in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) and the proportion of patients achieving HbA1c level $< 7.0\%$. Renal function parameters, such as eGFR and albumin/creatinine ratio, were also evaluated. Canagliflozin at a dose of 100 mg or 300 mg resulted in a significantly greater reduction in HbA1c at week 26 compared with placebo (–0.33%, –0.44%, and –0.03%). Canagliflozin also led to a more pronounced decrease in FPG, as well as a higher proportion of patients achieving

HbA1c level $< 7.0\%$ (27.3%, 32.6%, and 17.2% for Canagliflozin 100 mg, 300 mg, and placebo, respectively). In terms of safety, a slightly higher incidence of urinary tract infections and osmotic diuresis-related adverse events was observed with Canagliflozin 300 mg therapy. In conclusion, Canagliflozin improves glycemic control and is well tolerated in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and stage 3 chronic kidney disease (Yale et al. 2013).

The team of Fioretto evaluated the efficacy and safety of Dapagliflozin 10 mg versus placebo in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and moderate renal impairment (eGFR 45–59 mL/min/1.73 m²; chronic kidney disease stage 3A). A double-blind, parallel-group clinical trial was conducted involving patients with inadequately controlled type 2 diabetes mellitus (HbA1c 7.0–11.0%). Participants were randomized (1:1) to receive Dapagliflozin 10 mg once daily or a matching placebo for 24 weeks. At week 24, Dapagliflozin showed a significant advantage over placebo in terms of HbA1c level reduction (–0.34%), body weight reduction (–1.25 kg), fasting plasma glucose reduction (–0.9 mmol/L), and systolic blood pressure reduction (–3.1 mmHg). The decrease in eGFR from baseline was more pronounced with Dapagliflozin at week 24 (–2.49 mL/min/1.73 m²), but eGFR values returned to baseline by week 27 (+0.61 mL/min/1.73 m²). No increase in the incidence of adverse events (41.9% with Dapagliflozin versus 47.8% with placebo) or serious adverse events (5.6% versus 8.7%) was observed. No cases of bone fractures, limb amputations, or diabetic ketoacidosis were reported during the study (Fioretto et al. 2019).

The team of Barnett evaluated the efficacy and safety of Empagliflozin as an adjunctive therapy in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and chronic kidney disease (CKD). A randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, placebo-controlled clinical trial was conducted at 127 centers in 15 countries. Patients with stage 2 CKD (eGFR ≥ 60 to < 90 mL/min/1.73 m²) were randomized (1:1:1) to receive therapy with Empagliflozin 10 mg, Empagliflozin 25 mg, or placebo once daily for 52 weeks. Patients with stage 3 CKD (eGFR ≥ 30 to < 60 mL/min/1.73 m²)

Table 7. PICOS Bexagliflozin.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 312, with T2DM and chronic kidney disease (CKD) stage 3a or 3b, who took oral glucose-lowering therapy for 8 weeks. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.0%–10.5%. eGFR: 30–59 mL/min/1.73m ² . (Allegretti et al. 2019)	Bexagliflozin 20 mg/day	Placebo	Reduction of HbA1c level by: –0.61% with Bexagliflozin 20 mg. Participants with stage 3a CKD treated with Bexagliflozin had an average reduction in HbA1c levels by –0.65%, and those with stage 3b had an average reduction by –0.59%. Average weight reduction by –1.61 kg. Bexagliflozin reduced SBP by –3.8 mmHg and fasting plasma glucose levels with –0.76 mmol/L.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 25% of patients on Bexagliflozin therapy. Infections and infestations: Urinary tract infection: 6.37% with Bexagliflozin vs. 3.23% with placebo. Five genital mycotic infections in the arm on Bexagliflozin therapy. Nasopharyngitis: 7.01% Surgical and medical procedures: One limb amputation in the arm on Bexagliflozin therapy. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Seven fractures of the shoulder with Bexagliflozin Arthralgia: 5.73% Investigations: Increase in creatinine levels 0.08 mg/dL; eGFR reduction by 2.41 mL/min/1.73 m ² at week 24. Renal and urinary tract disorders: Acute kidney damage: 5.10% Polyuria: 7.64%	24-week, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicenter, multinational, randomized trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02836873
N = 386, with T2DM, aged ≥18 years, who took Metformin 1500 mg/day for at least ≥8 weeks prior to the start of the trial. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.0%–11.0%. BMI ≤45 kg m ² (Halvorsen et al. 2019)	Bexagliflozin 20 mg in combination with Metformin	Sitagliptin 100 mg in combination with Metformin	HbA1c level reduction: –0.74% in the Bexagliflozin 20 mg group and –0.82% in the Sitagliptin 100 mg group. Changes in FPG, body weight, and SBP were, respectively, with: –1.82 mmol/L, –3.35 kg, and –4.23 mmHg in the Bexagliflozin group and –1.45 mmol/L, –0.81 kg, and –1.90 mmHg in the Sitagliptin group.	Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infection: 2.6% Nasopharyngitis: 7.9% Urinary tract infection: 3.7% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 3.14% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria and polyuria: 2.1% Investigations: Increased hemoglobin and hematocrit; Serum uric acid reduction; Increase of HDL-C.	24-week, randomized, double-blind, active-controlled, parallel-group trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT03115112
N = 31, aged ≥20 years, taking Metformin 1500 mg/day. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.5%–12.0%. BMI ≤45 kg/m ² (Halvorsen et al. 2023a)	Bexagliflozin 20 mg in combination with Metformin	Placebo in combination with Metformin	HbA1c level reduction: –1.09% in the Bexagliflozin group and –0.56% in the placebo group. Baseline changes in SBP, FPG, and body weight were, respectively: –7.07 mmHg, –2.51 mmol/L, and –2.51 kg.	Infections and infestations: Genital mycotic infections: 1.9% Nasopharyngitis: 5.7% Urinary tract infection: 3.8% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 1.3% Renal and urinary tract disorders: Pollakiuria: 1.9% Polyuria: 3.16% Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Fracture: 0.6% Investigations: Hematocrit increase; HDL-C increase. Decrease of triglycerides and serum uric acid.	24-week, multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT03259789
N = 426, ≥18 years old, with T2DM, poorly controlled with Metformin therapy. BMI ≤ 45 kg/m ² Mean BMI: 31.83 kg/m ² Mean systolic blood pressure: 133.8 mmHg (Halvorsen et al. 2023b)	Bexagliflozin 20 mg, continued their therapy with Metformin	Glimepiride 2.4 or 6 mg once daily	HbA1c level reduction: –0.70% with Bexagliflozin 20 mg and –0.66% with Glimepiride. Body weight reduction: –3.71 kg with Bexagliflozin 20 mg compared to –0.60 kg with Glimepiride. Change in systolic blood pressure at week 60 in patients with baseline SBP ≥ 140 mmHg: –13.48 mmHg with Bexagliflozin 20 mg compared to –6.95 mmHg with Glimepiride.	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 13.62%. Urinary tract infection: 11.74% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 16.90% with Bexagliflozin 20 mg versus 33.33% with Glimepiride. Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Back pain: 2.82% Arthralgia: 6.10%	96-week, randomized, parallel-group, double-blind, active-controlled, phase 3 Trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02769481

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, body weight reduction, cardio-renal benefits)	Outcomes safety (adverse drug reactions evaluated by SOC of MedRA)	Study design
N = 1700, ≥ 40 years old, with poorly controlled T2DM. Baseline HbA1c level: 7.5%, increased cardiovascular risk. (Theracos Sub, LLC 2015)	Bexagliflozin 20 mg	Placebo	HbA1c level reduction: -0.85% with Bexagliflozin 20 mg Body weight reduction: -3.03 kg with Bexagliflozin 20 mg Change in systolic blood pressure: -9.83 mmHg with Bexagliflozin 20 mg	Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis: 8.48% Urinary tract infection: 11.31% Upper respiratory tract infection: 9.89% Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Hypoglycemia: 41.96% Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders: Arthralgia: 4.33% Back pain: 5.83% Gastrointestinal disorders: Diarrhea: 6.36% Nausea: 4.77%	24-week, randomized, parallel-group, placebo-controlled, phase 3 trial ClinicalTrials.gov ID: NCT02558296

Table 8. Types of adverse events and the number of clinical trials in which they were reported.

INN	System - organ class	Subgroup	Number of clinical trials reported	
Canagliflozin	Renal and urinary disorders	polyuria	6	
		pollakiuria	8	
		adverse reactions related to osmotic diuresis	8	
	Infections and infestations	urinary tract infection	12	
		genital mycotic infections	13	
		nasopharyngitis	1	
	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	hypoglycemia	14	
		Vascular disorders	orthostatic hypotension	1
	Investigations	increased ketone bodies	2	
		increased HDL-C	2	
		decrease in triglycerides	2	
		decrease in ASAT, ALAT, GGT	3	
	Dapagliflozin	Infections and infestations	urinary tract infection	8
genital mycotic infections			8	
nasopharyngitis			7	
Renal and urinary disorders		pollakiuria	2	
		Nervous system disorders	headache	4
Metabolism and nutrition disorders		hypoglycemia	7	
		Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders	back pain	4
Investigations			increased hematocrit	4
			decreased uric acid	4
		decreased triglycerides	2	
Empagliflozin	Infections and infestations	urinary tract infection	8	
		genital mycotic infections	8	
		nasopharyngitis	5	
		upper respiratory tract infection	4	
	Renal and urinary disorders	pollakiuria	2	
		Nervous system disorders	headache	2
	Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders	back pain	5	
		arthralgia	2	
		Gastrointestinal disorders	nausea	2
	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	hypoglycemia	8	
		Investigations	increased HDL-C	2
			increased hematocrit	3
	decreased serum uric acid	3		
Ertugliflozin	Infections and infestations	urinary tract infection	7	
		genital mycotic infections	7	
		nasopharyngitis	1	
	Renal and urinary disorders	polyuria	2	
		pollakiuria	2	
		Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders	fractures	1
	back pain		1	
	arthralgia		1	
	Vascular disorders		hypovolemia	4
	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	hypoglycemia	7	
Investigations		increased hematocrit	1	
	decreased serum uric acid	1		

INN	System - organ class	Subgroup	Number of clinical trials reported
Ipragliflozin	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	hypoglycemia	1
		Infections and infestations	urinary tract infection
	genital mycotic infections		1
	nasopharyngitis		2
	Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders		back pain
	Nervous system disorders	headache	1
	Renal and urinary disorders	pollakiuria	2
		polyuria	1
	Investigations	decreased triglycerides	2
		increased HDL-C	2
		decrease in ASAT and ALAT	1
	Bexagliflozin	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	hypoglycemia
Infections and infestations		urinary tract infection	5
		genital mycotic infections	3
		nasopharyngitis	4
Renal and urinary disorders		polyuria	2
		pollakiuria	2
		Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders	fractures
arthralgia			2
back pain			2
Surgical and medical procedures		amputation of a limb	1
		Investigations	increased hematocrit
			decrease in uric acid

were randomized (1:1) to receive Empagliflozin 25 mg or placebo for the same period. The primary endpoint was the change in HbA1c level from baseline at week 24. In patients with stage 2 CKD, the adjusted mean difference from placebo in the change in HbA1c level at week 24 was -0.52% for Empagliflozin 10 mg and -0.68% for Empagliflozin 25 mg. In patients with stage 3 CKD, the corresponding adjusted mean difference in HbA1c was -0.42% with Empagliflozin 25 mg. In conclusion, Empagliflozin was well tolerated and reduced HbA1c level in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and stage 2 or 3 CKD (Barnett et al. 2014).

Ji L et al. evaluated the efficacy and safety of Ertugliflozin in Asian patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus poorly controlled with Metformin. A 26-week, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial was conducted involving 506 Asian patients. Participants were randomized in a 1:1:1 ratio to receive placebo, Ertugliflozin 5 mg, or Ertugliflozin 15 mg once daily. The primary endpoint was the change in HbA1c level from baseline at week 26. Pre-specified secondary endpoints included changes in FPG, body weight, systolic and diastolic blood pressure (SBP/DBP), and the proportion of patients achieving HbA1c levels $< 7.0\%$. At week 26, the mean reduction in HbA1c was significantly greater with Ertugliflozin 5 mg and 15 mg compared with placebo (-1.0% , -0.9% , and -0.2% , respectively). Treatment with Ertugliflozin also led to a significant reduction in FPG, body weight, and systolic blood pressure. The proportion of patients achieving HbA1c $< 7.0\%$ was 16.2% with placebo, 38.2% with Ertugliflozin 5 mg, and 40.8% with Ertugliflozin 15 mg. The incidence of adverse events was similar between groups (59.3%, 56.5%, and 53.3% for placebo, Ertugliflozin 5 mg, and Ertugliflozin 15 mg, respectively). The incidence of symptomatic hypoglycemia was higher with Ertugliflozin 15 mg therapy compared with placebo (Ji et al. 2019).

Shestakova and Wilding evaluated the efficacy and safety of Ipragliflozin as an adjunctive therapy to Metformin in Russian patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. A double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial was conducted in 14 centers in Russia. A total of 165 participants were randomized in a 2:1 ratio to receive Ipragliflozin 50 mg/day or placebo for a period of 24 weeks, while continuing therapy with Metformin. As early as week 12, statistically significant reductions in HbA1c level and body weight were observed in favor of Ipragliflozin compared with placebo (mean difference -0.3% and -1.34 kg). The incidence of adverse events was similar between the two groups. In some patients, the dose was titrated to Ipragliflozin 100 mg/day, which led to an additional reduction in body weight (mean change from week 12: -0.65 kg) and a 13% increase in the proportion of patients achieving HbA1c $< 7.0\%$ at week 24. The incidence of adverse events remained similar in patients receiving Ipragliflozin 50 mg/day (23.7%) and Ipragliflozin 100 mg/day (24.6%). In conclusion, Ipragliflozin 50 mg/day as an adjunct to Metformin resulted in a significant improvement in glycemic control and weight reduction after 12 weeks and demonstrated a good safety profile. Titration of the dose to 100 mg/day further improved clinical outcomes (Shestakova et al. 2018).

Allegretti et al. evaluated the efficacy and safety of Bexagliflozin in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and chronic kidney disease (CKD). A phase 3, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicenter, multinational randomized clinical trial was conducted. Patients with CKD stage 3a or 3b, type 2 diabetes mellitus, HbA1c levels between 7.0% and 10.5%, and an eGFR of 30–59 mL/min/1.73 m², who had been on oral glucose-lowering therapy for at least eight weeks prior to the start of the trial. Participants were randomized to receive Bexagliflozin 20 mg once daily or a placebo for a period of 24 weeks. The primary endpoint

was the change in HbA1c level from baseline to week 24. Secondary endpoints included changes in body weight, systolic blood pressure, albuminuria, and HbA1c levels, stratified by CKD stage. Bexagliflozin resulted in a statistically significant reduction in HbA1c level of -0.37% compared with placebo. In patients with CKD stage 3a (eGFR $45\text{--}60\text{ mL/min/1.73 m}^2$) and stage 3b (eGFR $30\text{--}45\text{ mL/min/1.73 m}^2$), the reduction in HbA1c was -0.31% and -0.43% , respectively. In addition, Bexagliflozin significantly reduced body weight, systolic blood pressure, fasting plasma glucose levels (-0.76 mmol/L), and albuminuria (mean reduction in albumin/creatinine ratio of 20.1%). Urinary tract infections and genital mycotic infections were observed more frequently in patients treated with Bexagliflozin compared with placebo (Allegretti et al. 2019).

The incidence of documented hypoglycemia during the analyzed clinical trials was low in the treatment groups for all representatives of the SGLT2 inhibitors class when used as monotherapy. Common adverse drug reactions included urinary tract infections and genital mycotic infections. The incidence of polyuria and pollakiuria is the highest after administration of Canagliflozin. Back pain is observed after administration of Dapagliflozin and Empagliflozin. The incidence of nasopharyngitis is the highest after administration of Dapagliflozin and Empagliflozin. Increased levels of ketone bodies have been reported after administration of Canagliflozin. Increased hematocrit has been reported after administration of Dapagliflozin, Empagliflozin, Ertugliflozin, Ipragliflozin, and Bexagliflozin. A decrease in serum uric acid levels has been reported with Dapagliflozin, Empagliflozin, Ertugliflozin, and Bexagliflozin. Empagliflozin reduces albuminuria, which is a marker of glomerular impairment, in patients with chronic kidney disease. Triglyceride level decrease is observed with Canagliflozin, Dapagliflozin, Ipragliflozin, and Bexagliflozin. Increase in HDL-C level is seen after therapy with Canagliflozin, Empagliflozin, Ertugliflozin, Ipragliflozin, and Bexagliflozin. Fractures have been reported after administration of Ertugliflozin and Bexagliflozin. The safety profiles of all representatives of this class are similar. HbA1c reduction is the most significant after administration of Ertugliflozin 15 mg (-0.90%), Ipragliflozin 50 mg (-0.88%), and Canagliflozin 300 mg (-0.84%). The lowest change in HbA1c level is observed after administration of Dapagliflozin 2.5 mg (-0.60%), Dapagliflozin 5 mg (-0.68%), and Empagliflozin 10 mg (-0.66%). Body weight reduction is the most significant after administration of Ertugliflozin 15 mg with -2.93 kg and after administration of Canagliflozin 300 mg with -2.9 kg . In a comparative analysis between classes of GLP-1 receptor agonists and SGLT2 inhibitors, we found that GLP-1 receptor agonists and the dual GIP/GLP-1 receptor agonist Tirzepatide were superior to SGLT2 inhibitors in terms of decreasing HbA1c levels and reducing body weight. Gastrointestinal disorders are more common with GLP-1 receptor agonists, while SGLT2 inhibitors are more likely to cause kidney and urinary tract disorders. At the same time, based on the clinical trials analyzed,

SGLT2 inhibitors demonstrate more pronounced cardioprotective effects compared to GLP-1 receptor agonists (Petrova et al. 2024).

Conclusion

The results of the PICOS analysis of the efficacy and safety of SGLT2 inhibitors show that the most significant decrease in HbA1c levels is observed after administration of Ertugliflozin 15 mg (-0.90%), Ipragliflozin 50 mg (-0.88%), and Canagliflozin 300 mg (-0.84%). The reduction in body weight is most significant after treatment with Ertugliflozin 15 mg and Canagliflozin 300 mg , by -2.93 kg and -2.9 kg , respectively. All members of the class demonstrate a beneficial effect on blood pressure, expressed as a decrease in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure, as well as significant renal benefits, including a reduction in albuminuria. The inclusion of SGLT2 inhibitors in therapeutic algorithms represents a significant advance in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus, aimed at slowing disease progression and limiting the severity of associated complications.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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